

Advanced Avionics System Development: Achieving Systems Superiority through Design Automation

Gregory D. Peterson

John W. Hines

WL/AASH

Wright Laboratory, Avionics Directorate

2241 Avionics Circle Rm N3-F22

Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-7334

(937)-255-6653 ext. 3591

petersgd@aa.wpafb.af.mil

Abstract- Avionics systems in advanced aircraft provide the improved capability critical to achieving mission success for the war fighter. As the costs associated with aircraft avionics continue to mount, improved weapons system acquisition and support depends on cost-effective design methodologies and accurate design documentation. This paper explores how the standard hardware description language VHDL serves a critical role in effective acquisition of digital electronic systems.

With the ever-increasing complexity of systems and interdependency of hardware and software throughout the weapon system life cycle, it is imperative to facilitate the development of effective standards, methodologies, and tools which support the acquisition of complex systems consisting of sophisticated hardware and software. For cost-effective development of weapons systems which may have operational deployment spanning decades, program offices need to exploit the best commercial design practices and adapt them to support concurrent engineering considerations. Programs such as the DARPA Rapid Prototyping of Application Specific Signal Processors (RASSP) effort demonstrate 3X improvements in avionics system development by advocating approaches such as using COTS (Commercial Off The Shelf) parts, Model Year Upgrades, and virtual prototyping as techniques to leverage the economies of scale driving commercial electronics cost and performance improvements.

Wright Laboratory programs focusing on electronic systems design automation provide complementary improvements in design, documentation, and maintenance capabilities. Results from this research supports acquisition reform efforts to streamline the weapons system procurement process and provide contractors the flexibility to use the most effective

design management techniques. At the same time, while the Department of Defense (DoD) is moving away from dictating standards in contracting, the electronics industry continues to embrace open standards as a means to ensure hardware and software component compatibility. The question arises: what methodology and standards developments are necessary to support the continuing development of sophisticated weapons systems for the military? To address this question, the paper explores methodological needs for hardware and software design, manufacturability, test, and related issues to provide context and motivation before describing ongoing work to meet these needs.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. DESIGN METHODOLOGY
3. STANDARDS
4. CONCLUSIONS

1. INTRODUCTION

The electronics design industry enjoys dramatic improvements in circuit capabilities, with the number of transistors on a chip doubling every eighteen months as noted by Moore's Law [1]. This explosive growth represents tremendous potential for military and commercial electronics systems and components, while at the same time presenting designers with the seemingly insurmountable task of exploiting this growth effectively and economically. As a corollary to Moore's Law, the electronic systems design process demands an exponential increase in design productivity to keep pace with improvements in device density and speed.

Over the past twenty-five years, such large electronic design efforts as microprocessor development achieved increased circuit sizes from thousands to millions of devices primarily by enlarging design teams from tens to hundreds of engineers (and staff-years from scores to thousands) [2]. Within a decade, conservative estimates predict high-performance chips exceeding 100 million logic transistors and 1 GHz speed will be commercially available [3], thus rendering this strategy of achieving productivity improvements impractical for all but the largest and most critical design efforts. Decreasing feature sizes for devices create further demands because analog, electromagnetic, and atomic effects become more significant in submicron design, thus invalidating assumptions and models previously employed. Complicating matters further, the pace of technological innovation and the commercial market result in continuously shrinking product lifetimes for commercial parts and manufacturing processes.

Design methodologies and tools must account for these issues to ensure correct, efficient implementations of designs. Simply exploiting these improvements in designing and manufacturing electronics hardware solves only half the problem: we need efficient and reliable methods to develop and maintain both the hardware and software. With advances in reconfigurable computing, the delineation between these two domains continues to blur. Effective language support, tools, and methodologies addressing these issues will help enable the future deployment of sophisticated systems and the affordable, effective maintenance of existing weapons systems.

Large, complex weapons systems, including the avionics suite of advanced aircraft, often will be in service for decades and must target threats years away; hence, the system specifications must be very aggressive with respect to the capabilities required. In order to provide maximum system performance at the time of system deployment, the specification typically calls for technology significantly beyond the capabilities of commercially available electronic components at the time of specification. The aggressive system performance specification results in a costly, difficult, and time-intensive development effort, with relatively high risk due to the advanced nature of the required technology (which may depend on significant research developments). With the decade-long development cycle often found in fielding major new weapons systems, several generations of commercial processes for fabricating electronic devices will be developed and retired. Hence, any implementation using a particular process will likely suffer from an inability to fabricate additional parts for production or maintenance. Therefore, de-

signs suffer from an inability to acquire electronic parts combined with a significant lag in performance when compared to standard commercial parts [4].

One means of achieving affordable designs while improving performance and functionality is to use commercial off the shelf (COTS) parts to take advantage of the economies of scale, improvements in design automation, and the enhanced fabrication processes exploited by commercial parts. At the same time, efforts are required to prevent legacy parts acquisition problems due to the termination of the support of particular commercial parts. To do this, we need to capture the functionality in a portable manner to enable upgrading the design with model year upgrades effectively, thus allowing systems designers to enjoy the performance improvements provided by the commercial industry and to reduce the costs for electronic components.

In order to cost-effectively support the development of major weapons systems which may have operational deployment spanning decades, program offices need to exploit the best commercial design practices and adapt them to support concurrent engineering considerations. Programs such as the DARPA Rapid Prototyping of Application Specific Signal Processors (RASSP) effort advocate the use of COTS parts and Model Year Upgrades as techniques to leverage the economies of scale driving commercial electronics cost and performance improvements [5].

Acquisition reform efforts also attempt to streamline the weapons system procurement process and provide contractors the flexibility to use the most effective design management techniques. At the same time, while the DoD is moving away from dictating standards in contracting, the electronics industry continues to embrace open standards as a means to ensure hardware and software component compatibility. The question arises: what methodology and standards developments are necessary to support the continuing development of sophisticated weapons systems for the military? To address this question, we explore methodological needs for hardware and software design, manufacturability, test, and related issues. We then describe ongoing standards work to meet these needs.

2. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

In order to be able to adequately support a methodology for designing complex weapons systems, accurate specifications of function, timing, interface, and

constraints are needed, but must not be too restrictive of potential designs. The current standard practice for embedded systems design includes concurrent hardware and software development processes. The hardware and software design paths begin from an initial specification of the hardware based on preliminary software requirements. The hardware design effort then focuses on completing the hardware components of the system. Concurrently, the software design effort develops the software code for the system consistent with the initial hardware specification. When the hardware and software design tasks are complete, an integration and test process begins.

Often there is little interaction between the hardware and software design efforts because of a lack of a unified representation, simulation, and synthesis framework [6]. Because the integration and test phase of the design process is typically the first time the hardware and software are joined, a variety of problems are often encountered.

First, the lack of communications between the hardware and software design teams results in inconsistencies in the interpretation of design specifications, thus the hardware and software do not share the same view. This results in potentially incompatible development efforts.

Secondly, changes in the hardware design often are not communicated with the software design team, so the software is developed for the wrong hardware configuration.

Third, during integration and test, performance bottlenecks and hardware bugs are discovered. Due to the high cost of redesigning hardware, these problems are typically rectified by making modifications to the system software, resulting in code that is late and over budget. At this point, additional software engineers may be added to the effort, which can exacerbate the schedule and budget problems [7]. The software development effort often receives the blame for the overall project difficulties, when in reality the problems come from communications and coordination shortcomings during the specification and development.

To address this problem within systems design, the simultaneous consideration of hardware and software throughout the design process is needed. This is referred to as the *codesign* of hardware and software. Hardware/software codesign tasks include the specification of the system (sometimes referred to as *co-specification*), the concurrent software code generation and hardware development, and the verifica-

tion of the integrated system (typically via co-simulation of hardware and software models, executing software on emulated hardware, or physical prototyping). Note that the verification task needs to be performed throughout the system design effort, with different levels of detail being appropriate for each stage in the system development. Similarly, validation represents an important system design task. Design verification indicates the degree of conformance to the specification; whereas validation aims to ensure that the specification conforms to the needs and requirements of the customer.

Designers need to be able to specify systems containing hardware and software components in a manner independent of the particular implementation and mapping chosen. This specification method needs to support incomplete specifications in order to support the incremental development of systems and to provide the potential for adding capabilities further along in the life cycle as mission needs dictate and technology improvements allow. The specification needs to be able to collect functional and non-functional requirements for the system. Functional requirements include the algorithmic description of how the system behaves along with the timing. Non-functional requirements include considerations such as power, size, weight, manufacturability, reliability, maintainability, and cost. The CEENSS and RASSP programs advocate the use of simulatable or executable specifications which include the behavior (or function) of the system, a set of constraints (or non-functional requirements), and a test bench for verifying that the system meets functional requirements [8,9].

The system design activity includes concurrent and (hopefully) coordinated hardware and software design. Assuming the system specification includes a description of the entire system's behavior, this functionality must then be decomposed into some number of subsystems or blocks of functionality, which may be implemented in either hardware or software. This is referred to as *partitioning* the design.

Next, a candidate design architecture is developed including the decision about whether to implement each block in hardware or software. This design activity is *mapping*. Following the partitioning and mapping steps, some method must be employed to evaluate the candidate architecture to determine if it meets the system functional and non-functional requirements. This is often done by estimations and back-of-the-envelope calculations, but using the performance modeling techniques developed for

VHDL, the architecture can be evaluated with relative ease and fidelity [10].

Performance modeling with VHDL provides a mechanism for quickly evaluating different candidate system architectures by using a package of token-based VHDL constructs for the hardware elements, software modules, interconnection networks, and the data flowing through the system. Abstract models of processors, application specific integrated circuits, and interconnection networks focus on the amount of time spent on each token of data they handle before producing appropriate output tokens. As the hardware design progresses, more accurate models can be created to take into account design decisions and to enable modeling with higher fidelity.

Similarly, the software models may include different levels of detail ranging from an estimated instruction count, an estimate of the instruction mixes, to the final operational software code for each software module's processing. As the design progresses and more details are determined, the detail of the performance model can correspondingly increase. Capabilities for mixing models of different abstraction levels are needed in order to allow designers to flesh out areas of the system design at different rates. This arises when designers wish to study in more detail subsystems which have higher risk associated with their design or when portions of a design are reused [11].

Token-based performance modeling is a key capability in the system design process as it sheds light on possible inefficient or incorrect candidate partitions early enough to avoid wasted effort on rejected solutions. In efforts related to the design of advanced cockpit graphics systems, dozens of potential architectures were developed and evaluated using performance modeling techniques, thus enabling the design team to consider many more tradeoffs than traditional design methodologies would allow. At the same time, using a performance modeling-based design methodology helps in validating the design and the specification [12].

Another key aspect of an effective design methodology is the notion of using test benches throughout the design of a system. All too often, the design of a system begins with the creation of a specification followed by the implementation of the component hardware and software parts. Testing is too often performed in an ad hoc manner, with tests often developed to ensure the components operate consistently with how the designer interprets the specification. Tests should be developed by someone other

than the designer to reduce the likelihood of errors in interpreting the specification. A major problem is the lack of a global view of what tests should be performed on a system and its components to ensure the whole and the parts operate as intended. The test methodology we advocate is the creation of test benches as the first step in the design process. This forces designers to step back to consider the intended operation of a system, what types of tests can be performed, and how to structure the testing to provide maximum benefit. The test plan development should overlap with the specification effort, and should include considering what tests will be applied in order to convince the customer the design meets the specification.

In addition to the functional aspects of a subsystem or component, we need to capture non-functional requirements including constraints on size, weight, power dissipation, and other physical characteristics. In addition, constraints on fabrication processes, materials, and machines impact the manufacturability of system components and the capability to redesign the components later in the system's life cycle. Although these constraints impact activities late in the design cycle, early consideration of these constraints can minimize the adverse effects of manufacturing problems.

The Wright Laboratory Continuous Electronics Enhancement Using Simulatable Specifications (CEENSS) program addresses these methodology needs by supporting the development of simulatable (or executable) specifications⁸. A simulatable specification, or SimSpec, includes a VHDL description of the function and timing which is simulatable, a test bench with stimuli and expected responses to provide a means for signing off on the design and ensuring correctness, and constraints including such aspects as size, weight, cost, power dissipation, manufacturability, reliability, and maintainability. A SimSpec can then be decomposed into subsystems or components, each with their own SimSpec, as a means of standardizing the design documentation information content to support reuse or redesign. The CEENSS SimSpec methodology provides the necessary form, fit, function, interface, and constraint information necessary to support streamlined acquisition of weapons systems programs.

The use of SimSpecs improves the quality of system acquisition efforts by providing a well-defined structure for various pieces of design information as described above. Moreover, the use of SimSpecs does not over-constrain the system designers, as any number of effective design methodologies can exploit SimSpecs. An effective means of using Sim-

Specs, design reuse, and advanced electronic design automation techniques is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The RASSP design process

During system definition, a requirements and functional analysis effort results in the creation of an initial SimSpec. This SimSpec is then used as a basis for the functional design effort. Architectural selection activities based on the performance modeling techniques discussed above enable the evaluation of perhaps dozens of candidate system architectures. Once a candidate architecture is selected, a more detailed system model helps to verify its suitability. The architecture selection and verification efforts include increasingly detailed models of the hardware, software, and operating system components. This technique of using models of systems components, or *virtual prototyping*, as opposed to building physical prototypes saves considerable expense and effort by helping find errors earlier and before spending significant time and money in building system prototypes⁴.

With development times as long as ten years (or even more), systems design methodologies need to be able to support a relatively painless migration across processes. This includes the capability to easily re-partition designs and synthesize or autocode the subsystems or components. Using virtual prototyp-

ing and model year upgrades (inserting improved commercial parts periodically to take advantage of commercial performance and cost improvements) provides this capability⁵. This is the only effective and affordable way for us to support weapons systems acquisition now and in the future.

By following this methodology, additional time and cost may be spent at the beginning of the design process. Because 90% of a system's life cycle costs are determined in the first 10% of a program, this extra time and cost will be well worth the effort. In one radar system program, the creation of a comprehensive test plan and methodology resulted in a 20% increase in the specification development time. The test plan work did result in the early detection of numerous specification errors which would certainly have resulted in a much longer schedule and greater cost impact than the test plan development. In addition, the confidence in the specification and the consideration of complex interactions of radar modes, considerably reduced the risk in the radar system development effort.

3. STANDARDS

In light of the improvements in productivity in the commercial sector, acquisition reform aims to maximize flexibility in order take advantage of the best practices. In keeping with this goal, standards are not being dictated as often in weapon systems acquisition efforts in order to allow contractors to decide which standards, if any, are the most appropriate for any given task. Because of the unique needs of the DoD and Air Force, some care must be taken to ensure systems can be effective and affordable for decades. Therefore, the DoD and Air Force continue the support and development for Ada, the ISO standard software language, and VHDL, the IEEE standard hardware description language.

Due to its tremendous software industry acceptance, the Java language offers notable potential for DoD systems acquisition, but has not yet been standardized. Additional development for real-time support and experience with its use for large systems development also remain before wide-spread adoption for weapons system acquisition would be prudent. The Java virtual machine model may ease the incremental upgrading of processors with advancing technology by providing a "veneer" which masks many of the details of the specific processor employed. Due to the many similarities of Java and Ada [13], Intermetrics Inc. has developed tools to compile Ada source code into Java byte codes for use with Java Virtual Machines [14].

Long-term software engineering experience proves Ada to be effective for cost-effectively managing large program development and maintenance efforts, particularly when compared to languages such as C [15,16]. Despite the end of the DoD Ada mandate, Ada remains a powerful language often chosen for weapons systems development [17]. Ada provides strong typing, encapsulation via the package mechanism, and supports generics among other features. For similar reasons, VHDL provides the best current capability for supporting the development and ongoing maintenance of large, complex digital systems.

Several past and current research and standardization efforts focus on ways to extend the capabilities of VHDL to better support systems design and, in particular, to provide an integrated mechanism for modeling, simulation, and synthesis of software components [18]. Although, as a hardware description language, VHDL has characteristics which differentiate it from software programming languages, system and hardware design tools and methodologies can potentially benefit significantly from the improvements made in software engineering. One effort to transition software engineering standard practices into hardware description languages is the work focused on creating object-oriented VHDL extensions.

Object-oriented software languages and methodologies provide mechanisms for supporting abstraction, encapsulation, extensibility, reusability and maintainability. Although many of these capabilities already exist, at least in a limited form [19], efforts are underway to expand these capabilities. Object-oriented extensions to VHDL promise improvements in the capability to reuse models, help to make models more understandable, enhance the productivity and flexibility of designers, and to reduce problems associated with modeling the interaction of object-oriented software code with VHDL models of hardware elements. A number of proposed language changes and preliminary implementations exist, but debate continues to rage concerning what specific capabilities are needed and what impact they will have on tools and methodologies [20].

Complex systems include both hardware and software components. Significant recent attention focuses on how to specify, design, and verify the hardware and software together. Current VHDL standardization efforts related to codesign focus on co-simulation approaches in the short term [21] and general codesign support in the long term [22].

In response to a perceived need for additional support of abstract system design and specification, a system-level design language development effort sponsored by the Industry Council continues to investigate needs in this area in preparation for extensions to VHDL or the possible development a new hardware description language [23].

Analog/mixed signal issues are being addressed with the VHDL-AMS standard based on VHDL. As submicron designs continue to increase clock speeds and decrease feature sizes, the interconnection of logic will become the most important aspect of digital design. Currently, and for the past two decades, we have been able to ignore most of the analog effects when designing digital circuitry. Continuing improvements in fabrication processes yield fast and small circuits, but the interconnects between logic increasingly act as antennas and suffer from cross-coupling. Similarly, matching impedances is becoming more difficult and important as interconnects suffer from transmission line reflective effects. The VHDL-AMS standard provides a language in which both digital and analog circuitry effects can be modeled, thus giving us a tool for considering these analog effects for advanced digital design.

Ongoing standards work supported by the DoD includes work related to the Advanced Intermediate Representation with Extensibility (AIRE) standard intermediate format for VHDL, VHDL-AMS, and Verilog [24]. The AIRE standard provides a means for compliant tools to interoperate, thus reducing portability problems and enabling focused research and development of tools for specific needs throughout the design process.

In order to standardize the type of information included in particular types of models, a modeling taxonomy from the RASSP program defines a number of model classes and the information contained within each [25]. This effort helps reduce problems arising from inconsistent nomenclature and aids in understanding the purpose and capabilities of given models.

Helping to tie together many of the electronics design industry needs for standards, a standards roadmap was created to help identify some of the gaps in the standards supporting hardware design to help prioritize the investment of resources for standardization activities¹⁵. This roadmap does not address domains such as software and is focused on commercial, not military, needs; nonetheless, it provides a good overview of what standards are

currently defined and helps illuminate areas for future work.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Weapons system acquisition, now and in the future, continues to depend on effective design methodologies employing standards. VHDL and Ada provide capabilities critical to the development and support of weapons systems with lifetimes spanning decades. Effective electronic weapons system acquisition benefits from approaches which unleash the full capabilities of VHDL. Modeling methods exploiting techniques such as SimSpecs are critical to transforming the DoD weapons system acquisition process to become cost-effective and timely.

In order to adequately develop complicated systems in an efficient manner, designers must employ a structured, repeatable design process. Such a process should employ standard tools and languages. The tools are cheaper and more readily available. Engineers with expertise in the tools and languages exist. Commercial design efforts help to improve the tools and languages by providing larger markets, hence we exploit the economies of scale for tools and design capabilities, not just for the physical parts themselves.

Similarly, in order to adequately enable maintenance and redesign of these systems, high quality and portable, tool-independent documentation of the design must be a high priority for the system program office and the contractor. Shortening life cycles make parts obsolescence inevitable, and the onset of the obsolescence issue becomes more acute when the system is not developed with upgrades and retrofits in mind. Improved capabilities for redesign and retrofitting also makes it easier to reuse the system, or associated subsystems, in other related systems.

Finally, the acquisition reform goal of empowering weapon systems contractors to employ the best commercial practices in developing DoD systems hinges on supporting agile design processes which exploit state-of-the-art technologies and design tools. Such an approach of employing language-based systems design improves productivity while at the same time providing critical documentation. Experience with such a virtual prototyping electronics system design approach demonstrates reduced product development time due to earlier detection of errors and associated reduction in the integration and test tasks.

Ongoing DoD/Air Force efforts, including research and development work at the Air Force Research Laboratory and DARPA continue to address the important problems facing program offices in the acquisition of advanced air and space electronic systems. Applying many of the advances described in this paper should improve the engineering manufacturing and development and production of systems while providing information critical to lifetime support and upgrade to keep our weapons systems effective when they are needed.

[1] Gordon Moore. VLSI: Some Fundamental Challenges. *IEEE Spectrum*, 16(4):30-37, April 1979.

[2] Sematech, EDA Standards Roadmap Council, 6 July 1995.

[3] EDA Technologies Directions Workshop, November 1995.

[4] G. Caracciolo and J. Pridmore. Reuse-Oriented Model Year Architectures for Rapid Prototyping. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Annual RASSP Conference*, pages 197-200, July, 1995.

[5] W. Hood *et al.* RASSP Program Overview. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Annual RASSP Conference*, pages 1-18, July, 1995.

[6] Asawaree Kalavade and Edward Lee. A Hardware/Software Codesign Methodology for DSP Applications. *IEEE Design & Test of Computers*, pages 16-28, September 1993.

[7] F. P. Brooks, Jr. *The Mythical Man-Month: Essays on Software Engineering*, Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1975.

[8] Mark Thullen. Simulatable Specifications and VHDL in Top-Down Design. In *Proceedings of the Spring VHDL International Users' Forum*, pages 293-304, March 1996.

[9] Vijay Madiseti and Jack Corley. Rapid Prototyping of Application Specific Signal Processors: Current Practice, Challenges, and Roadmap. *RASSP Digest*, 2(2):13-18. June 1996.

[10] Sanjaya Kumar and Fred Rose. Integrated Simulation of Performance Models and Behavioral Models. In *Proceedings of the Fall VHDL International Users' Forum*, pages 185-194, October 1996.

[11] Fred Rose *et al.* A Model for the Coanalysis of Hardware and Software Architectures. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Hardware/Software Codesign*, pages 94-103, March, 1996.

[12] B.C. Read III, *et al.*, Developing the Next Generation Cockpit Display System. In *Proceedings of the 48th National Aerospace and Electronics Conference*. Dayton, OH 20-23 May 1996.

[13] Tucker Taft. "Programming the Internet in Ada 95". In *Proceedings of the 1996 Ada-Europe International Conference on Reliable Software Technologies*, Montreux, Switzerland, June 10-14, 1996. Berlin, Germany: Springer-Verlag. pp. 1-16.

-
- [14] See <http://www.appletmagic.com/>
- [15] Stephen Zeigler. Comparing Development Costs of C and Ada. See http://sw-eng.falls-church.va.us/AdaC/docs/reports/cada/cada_art.html.
- [16] P.K. Lawlis and T.W. Elam. Ada Outperforms Assembly: A Case Study. In *Proceedings of TRI-Ada*, 1992.
- [17] Lynne Hamilton-Jones, Kenneth Littlejohn, Marc Pitarys. Software Technology for Next-Generation Strike Fighter Avionics. *DASC*. Atlanta, GA 27-31 October 1997.
- [18] John Teets. The EDA Standards Roadmap and the EDA Industry Council. *RASSP Digest*, 3(3):44-45. September 1996.
- [19] Wolfgang Ecker. An Object-Oriented View of Structural VHDL Description. In *Proceedings of the Spring VHDL International Users' Forum*, pages 255-264, March 1996.
- [20] See <http://vhdl.org/vi/oovhdl/>
- [21] M. Mills and G. Peterson. Requirements and Concepts for Hardware/Software Codesign. To appear in *Proceedings of the Spring VHDL International Users' Forum*, April 1997.
- [22] See <http://vhdl.org/vi/codesign/>
- [23] System Level Design Workshop, October, 1996.
- [24] John Willis *et al.* Advanced Intermediate Representation with Extensibility (AIRE). In *Proceedings of the Fall VHDL International Users' Forum*, pages 33-40, October 1996.
- [25] Carl Hein *et al.* Effecting VHDL Model Interoperability in RASSP through a Common Modeling Taxonomy. In *Proceedings of the Fall VHDL International Users' Forum*, pages 8.29-8.37, October 1995.